

2029 Coastal Master Plan: Flood Insurance Implications of 2023 Coastal Master Plan Future Scenarios and Projects

Final Report of Task 4 – Flood Insurance Affordability Metrics Development

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Task Overview

Within this task, we develop and evaluate metrics for assessing flood insurance affordability in Coastal Louisiana. We analyze the impact of restoration and risk reduction projects on insurance affordability, providing insights into the effectiveness of CPRA restoration and risk reduction projects.

Table of Contents

Task Overview	2
List of Tables	4
List of Figures	5
Abbreviations	6
1.0 Introduction	7
2.0 Methodology	8
2.1 Overview of Affordability Framework	8
2.2 Data Sources	9
2.3 FIA Metric Computation Steps	10
3.0 Results of FIA Analysis and Project Impact Evaluation	10
3.1 Baseline FIA Under Future Without Action (FWOA)	10
Long-Term Decline in Affordability	10
3.2 Predicted Impact of MP23 Restoration and Risk Reduction Project Implementation on Flood Insurance Affordability	12
3.2.1 Results	12
3.2.2 Interpretation	14
3.2.3 Block Groups with Greatest Affordability Decline	16
3.2.4 Insurance Premium Reduction	17
4.0 Conclusions	20
References	21
Appendix A. Spatial Distribution of Flood Insurance Affordability ($FIA \geq 100$)	22
Supplementary Materials	30

List of Tables

Table 1. Summary of MP23 Project Implementation Impact on Flood Insurance Affordability..	13
Table 2. Paired block-group comparisons of FWOA and FWMP outcomes across scenarios and years. Reported metrics include mean differences (Δ), 95% confidence intervals, p-values, and effect sizes (r), for both median FIA and percent affordable structures.	14
Table 3. Change in % Affordable Structures ($FIA \geq 100$) Between Year 12 and Year 52 (Top 10 Worst-Affected Block Groups Under FWOA, Higher). Changes are percentage points (pp).	16

List of Figures

Figure 1. Median Flood Insurance Affordability by Block Group – Year 12 (FWOA), Scenario: (a) Lower, (b) Higher.....	11
Figure 2. Change in percent Affordability – Year 12 to 52 (FWOA, Higher)	12
Figure 3. Change in percent Affordability – Year 12 to 52 (FWMP, Higher)	15
Figure 4. Net Improvement in Flood Insurance Affordability Due to MP23 Restoration and Risk Reduction Project Implementation (Δ % Affordable, FWMP – FWOA, Year 12 to 52, Higher) 16	
Figure 5. (a) Total Premiums Over 50 Years, Future With and Without Action, Higher and Lower Scenario; (b) annual premium savings (FWMP–FWOA) Over 50 Years, Higher and Lower Scenario.	18
Figure 6. Insurance Premium Savings (USD) at Block-group Level, (a) Year 12, Higher; (b) Year 22, Higher.....	19

Abbreviations

ACS	American Community Survey
CLARA	Coastal Louisiana Risk Assessment
MP23	Louisiana’s 2023 Coastal Master Plan
CPRA	Coastal Protection and Restoration Authority
DSS	Data Storage System
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FIA	Flood Insurance Affordability
FWMP	Future With Master Plan
FWOA	Future Without Action
GEOID	Geographic Identifier (Census block group ID)
HUD	U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development
IPUMS	Integrated Public Use Microdata Series
MEDINC	Median Family Income
NFIP	National Flood Insurance Program
QR	Qualifying Ratio
RBP	Risk-Based Premium
RR2.0	Risk Rating 2.0
SFHA	Special Flood Hazard Area

1.0 Introduction

Flood insurance affordability is an emerging concern at the intersection of climate adaptation, housing affordability, and flood risk management in the United States. As flood risks intensify due to sea level rise, more intense storm events, and land subsidence, insurance premiums are rising, placing additional financial strain on low- and moderate-income households, who often reside in flood-prone regions. In Louisiana, where the majority of the population lives in or near coastal or riverine floodplains, the challenge is particularly acute.

Housing affordability in the United States has long been defined using a benchmark set by the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development (HUD): a household is considered cost-burdened if it spends more than 30% of its gross income on housing-related costs, including insurance. However, this benchmark is increasingly exceeded due to structural constraints such as restrictive zoning, limited supply of affordable housing, and long commuting distances (Hamidi et al., 2018). These constraints have pushed many low-income families into more vulnerable, high-risk flood zones, exposing them to growing insurance burdens as well as physical flood risk. Recent research underscores the disproportionate impact of housing and insurance cost burdens on very low-income populations. Households earning below regional median incomes, especially renters, often lack the resources to absorb increases in premiums or to invest in mitigation strategies that could reduce risk (Kousky & Kunreuther, 2013; FEMA, 2018). As flood risk increases due to the increasing frequency and severity of storms and as new flood risk models inform premium setting, the affordability crisis becomes a dual challenge: how to protect households from flood events while ensuring that insurance remains accessible.

FEMA's new National Flood Insurance Program (NFIP) pricing approach, known as Risk Rating 2.0 (RR2.0), has placed significant financial strain on coastal Louisiana residents. Based on FEMA's published data on NFIP policy premiums under Risk Rating 2.0, we estimate that coastal Louisiana residents are experiencing an average increase of approximately 306% in flood insurance premiums compared to the legacy rating system (calculation based on FEMA, 2022). RR2.0 has exacerbated disparities in housing affordability in coastal regions, disproportionately impacting vulnerable communities and populations (risQ, 2021). While RR2.0 aims to reflect actuarial fairness, it has also exacerbated disparities in flood insurance affordability, raising concerns about long-term resilience. Notably, RR2.0 does not yet directly account for community-scale flood risk reduction or coastal restoration projects implemented under Louisiana's Coastal Master Plan. Only measures that are incorporated into updated FEMA flood maps or already represented in the National Levee Database (e.g., accredited levee systems) are reflected in NFIP pricing. As a result, the premium impacts of large-scale projects such as marsh creation, hydrologic restoration, and other non-levee restoration measures are not captured in current RR2.0 rates. This disconnect between engineered risk reduction and premium setting has raised questions about how public investments in mitigation affect insurance costs.

The Coastal Protection and Restoration Authority (CPRA) is Louisiana's lead agency for implementing large-scale restoration and flood risk reduction projects across the state's coastal zone. The Louisiana Coastal Master Plan (MP) guides the investment of billions of dollars in flood protection systems, barrier islands, wetlands restoration, and community resilience initiatives aimed at reducing future flood damage. However, despite their physical benefits, the impact of master plan projects on RR2.0 insurance premiums remain poorly understood. There is a clear need to assess how the implementation of master plan projects could translate into reduced insurance burdens for households and communities. As part of this initiative, our project

titled "2029 Louisiana Coastal Master Plan: 2023 Coastal Master Plan Flood Insurance Implications of Future Scenarios and Projects" focuses on understanding the implications of future environmental scenarios and restoration and risk reduction projects on flood insurance premiums and affordability under the RR2.0 framework. The analysis uses scenarios and projects from the 2023 Coastal Master Plan (MP23), as MP29 scenarios and projects are not yet available. Our approach includes developing and integrating new methods and models to assess insurance costs, affordability metrics, and the potential influence of proposed restoration and risk reduction projects.

Within Task 4 of this project, we develop and apply a Flood Insurance Affordability (FIA) metric to assess how premiums, under RR2.0, affect households in terms of affordability. Our key objectives in Task 4 are to:

- Develop a robust, data-driven methodology for estimating flood insurance affordability across coastal Louisiana;
- Analyze the spatial distribution of affordability across census block groups using American Community Survey (ACS)-derived income data;
- Evaluate the effect of restoration and risk reduction projects, as represented in CPRA MP23 scenarios, on flood insurance affordability;
- Provide insights into how the state's risk reduction and restoration investments may contribute to financial resilience (improved affordability).

This report documents the development and application of the FIA metric using RR2.0-modeled premiums under varying scenarios as defined in the 2023 CMP. The analysis builds upon the premium outputs generated in Task 3, which estimated RR2.0 premiums for structures from the Coastal Louisiana Risk Assessment model (CLARA) asset inventory. Task 4 now expands this work by assessing how those premiums interact with local income data to determine where affordability challenges are most severe and how they may be alleviated through planned interventions.

2.0 Methodology

This section describes the methodological framework used to estimate the FIA metric across coastal Louisiana census block groups. The FIA metric is designed to assess whether modeled flood insurance premiums, under different scenarios, exceed established thresholds of affordability for typical households within each geographic area. The analysis integrates model-generated premium outputs, U.S. Census income data, and policy-justified affordability benchmarks to compute FIA metric spatially.

2.1 Overview of Affordability Framework

For this analysis, a measure of flood insurance affordability is estimated similarly to how housing affordability is determined for qualifying for a mortgage loan. This parallel framework is used because both housing and flood insurance affordability involve evaluating whether a recurring housing-related cost exceeds a reasonable portion of household income. In the absence of a standardized federal definition for affordable flood insurance, mirroring the housing affordability approach provides a clear, policy-consistent rationale and enables interpretation using familiar financial benchmarks. This approach aligns with FEMA's 2018 National Flood Insurance Program Affordability Framework, which also draws on established housing affordability concepts to assess premium burden relative to income.

Housing affordability is traditionally estimated by comparing the median family income (MEDINC) to the qualifying income for housing (QINC_H). The MEDINC is retrieved from the ACS. The QINC_H is the necessary income to qualify for the mortgage loan. The monthly payment of this loan is based on the monthly mortgage rate/effective mortgage rate and is calculated using median home price and interest rate considering 20 percent down payment. HUD defines affordability using a qualifying ratio (QR) of 25%, meaning that households should not spend more than 25% of income on mortgage payments. The QINC_H is then estimated using the monthly payments and the QR.

In the case of flood insurance affordability, the monthly payment will be the premium value that one needs to pay to keep the flood insurance. Once a QR value is fixed, the qualifying income for insurance (QINC_INS) can be calculated by dividing the flood insurance premium value (RBP) by the QR (Equation 1). Then the FIA is calculated by comparing the MEDINC and the QINC_INS (Equation 2).

$$QINC_INS = \left(\frac{RBP}{QR}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$FIA = \left(\frac{MEDINC}{QINC_INS}\right) * 100 \quad (2)$$

Interpretation (QR=2%):

- FIA = 100 → A household at the block group’s MEDINC spends exactly 2% of income on flood insurance (affordable).
- FIA > 100 → Flood insurance is affordable (premium burden is less than 2% of MEDINC).
- FIA < 100 → Flood insurance is unaffordable (premium burden exceeds 2% of MEDINC).

The QR values used in this analysis are grounded in FEMA’s 2018 Affordability Framework for the National Flood Insurance Program, federal housing affordability standards established by HUD and peer-reviewed literatures (e.g., Kousky & Kunreuther, 2014). A 2% threshold is applied to evaluate affordability for homeowners, consistent with FEMA’s recommendation to assess flood insurance burden as a percentage of household income. FEMA’s own analysis (Table 2.8) indicates that approximately 24% of policyholders residing within Special Flood Hazard Areas (SFHAs) spend between 1% and 2% of their income on flood insurance, and an additional 11% exceed 2%. This shows that a significant proportion of households experience affordability pressures above the 2% threshold.

2.2 Data Sources

The following data inputs were used for the FIA computation:

- Modeled Premium Data:
Premiums were generated using the Batch_RR2 model, which simulates flood insurance costs under RR2.0 system for a comprehensive set of residential structures from CLARA asset database across coastal Louisiana.
- Income Data (ACS):
Median Family Income (MEDINC) is used in this study as the income measure for evaluating affordability. MEDINC in the Past 12 Months (in 2023 Inflation-Adjusted Dollars) was extracted at the census block group level from the ACS 5-Year Estimates, Table B19113. This table was accessed via IPUMS NHGIS (Schroeder et al., 2025)

Each structure was assigned the MEDINC corresponding to the block group in which it is located.

- **Geographic Data:**
A shapefile of Louisiana census block groups was used to spatially join each structure to its block group and link it to the appropriate MEDINC value. All spatial operations were conducted in Python using GeoPandas.

2.3 FIA Metric Computation Steps

The following computational workflow was used to derive the FIA metric:

- Structures were assigned to census block groups via spatial join using geographic coordinates.
- Each structure was linked to its block group's MEDINC.
- For each structure, the RR2.0 annual premiums (RBP) were extracted from Batch_RR2 model outputs.
- A threshold of 2% of MEDINC was applied.
- For each structure, FIA value was estimated using Equation 1 and 2.
- To assess affordability patterns at higher geographic levels, the number and percentage of unaffordable structures were aggregated by block group.

3.0 Results of FIA Analysis and Project Impact Evaluation

This section presents the results of the FIA analysis conducted across all modeled structures in coastal Louisiana. Results are reported in terms of:

- FIA scores
- Percent of Affordable Structures ($FIA \geq 100$) – representing the share of households for whom flood insurance premiums are deemed affordable based on the 2% income threshold.

3.1 Baseline FIA Under Future Without Action (FWOA)

To understand the future trajectory of affordability, we analyzed affordability across five future time horizons under the MP23 FWOA scenarios (CPRA, 2023). Using modeled full-risk premiums and MEDINC from the ACS, we computed the FIA metric for each structure and aggregated the results at the block group level. The percent of structures deemed affordable (i.e., $FIA \geq 100$) was calculated for each block group at years 12, 22, 32, 42, and 52 for both Higher and Lower environmental scenarios from MP23.

Long-Term Decline in Affordability

Across most of the region, flood insurance affordability is projected to decline steadily over time under the MP23 FWOA scenarios. These impacts are especially pronounced in low-lying and economically vulnerable areas.

To illustrate the spatial distribution of baseline affordability, Figure 1 presents the percent of structures deemed affordable ($FIA \geq 100$) at Year 12 under both the Lower and Higher environmental scenario, highlighting areas where flood insurance was already out of reach for most households early in the planning horizon.

Figure 1. Median Flood Insurance Affordability by Block Group – Year 12 (FWOA), Scenario: (a) Lower, (b) Higher

To assess the long-term trend, we calculated the change in the percentage of affordable structures between Year 12 and Year 52 for each census block group. As shown in Figure 2 the spatial change under the Higher environmental scenario, the distribution is skewed toward small losses: many block groups exhibit little to no change (0 to about –2 percentage points), and a broad set shows modest declines on the order of –5 to –15 percentage points. Localized hotspots experience much larger deterioration, with declines of –30 to –70 percentage points, and a handful of extreme cases exceeding –80 percentage points. Conversely, a small number of block groups remain stable or improve, generally by $\leq +1$ percentage point, with rare larger gains (up

to ~+21 percentage points). This pattern indicates a region-wide mild decline with concentrated areas of severe affordability loss.

Figure 2. Change in percent Affordability – Year 12 to 52 (FWOA, Higher)

3.2 Predicted Impact of MP23 Restoration and Risk Reduction Project Implementation on Flood Insurance Affordability

To evaluate the effect of MP23 restoration and risk reduction projects on flood insurance affordability, we compared affordability outcomes between the FWOA and FWMP conditions across five planning horizons (years 12, 22, 32, 42, 52) and two environmental scenarios (Higher and Lower).

These comparisons are based on modeled premiums generated using the Batch_RR2 tool. The FWOA scenarios reflect baseline flood conditions without project implementation, while the FWMP scenario predicts the cumulative effects of MP23 restoration and risk reduction projects. The resulting premiums were evaluated using the FIA metric to determine whether MP23 project implementation is predicted to improve the affordability of flood insurance at the block group level.

3.2.1 Results

The analysis shows a consistent improvement in flood insurance affordability under the FWMP condition across all years and both environmental scenarios. Key findings include:

- On average, median FIA values increased by up to 8.16 points in the Higher scenario by year 52, and up to 8.02 points in the Lower scenario by Year 52, indicating a reduction in premiums relative to local income due to risk reduction project implementation.
- The percentage of structures meeting the affordability threshold ($FIA \geq 100$) increased by up to 3.30% in the Higher scenario and 3.24% in the Lower scenario by year 52. This means more households are projected to afford insurance with implementation of MP23 projects.

- The percentage of block groups showing improvement in affordability rises over time, reaching nearly 29% of all block groups under the Higher scenario and 25% under the Lower scenario by year 52.

A summary of average changes with MP23 implementation versus without is presented in the table below:

Table 1. Summary of MP23 Project Implementation Impact on Flood Insurance Affordability

Scenario	Year	Avg Median FIA (FWOA)	Avg Median FIA (FWMP)	Avg Δ Median FIA (FWMP – FWOA)	Avg % Affordable (FWOA)	Avg % Affordable (FWMP)	Avg Δ % Affordable (FWMP – FWOA)	% Blocks Improved
Higher	12	175.28	176.52	1.24	60.44	61.04	0.61	14.73
Higher	22	174.36	176.3	1.94	59.96	60.62	0.66	18.1
Higher	32	170.84	176.09	5.24	58.35	60.56	2.21	23.1
Higher	42	166.3	174.04	7.74	56.48	59.59	3.11	25.82
Higher	52	162.69	170.85	8.16	55.07	58.38	3.3	28.91
Lower	12	175.5	176.55	1.05	60.55	61.06	0.52	13.48
Lower	22	174.99	177.03	2.04	60.26	60.97	0.71	18.15
Lower	32	174.37	177.07	2.7	59.97	61	1.04	19.29
Lower	42	171.12	176.52	5.41	58.49	60.8	2.31	22.61
Lower	52	167.2	175.22	8.02	56.95	60.18	3.24	25.49

Notes:

- Δ Median FIA reflects the average increase in median FIA scores per block group.
- Δ % Affordable indicates the increase in the share of structures with FIA ≥ 100.
- % of Block Groups Improved is the proportion of block groups where affordability improved (i.e., positive Δ % Affordable).

To assess whether the observed differences between FWOA and FWMP represent statistically significant improvements in affordability outcomes, we conducted paired block-group tests across all scenarios and years. For each scenario and year, we compared block-group level outcomes between FWOA and FWMP using paired statistical tests. Normality of differences was assessed with the Shapiro–Wilk test. As the differences were consistently non-normal, we applied the Wilcoxon signed-rank test to evaluate whether FWMP significantly improved outcomes relative to FWOA. We report mean deltas, 95% confidence intervals, p-values, and effect sizes (r) to describe both statistical and practical significance (Table 2).

For both metrics, median FIA and the percent of affordable structures, FWMP consistently outperformed FWOA. For example, in the Higher scenario at Year 52, the median FIA was higher under FWMP by an average of 8.16 points (95% CI [6.96, 9.36], $p < 10^{-96}$, $r = 0.49$), and the proportion of affordable structures increased by 3.30 percentage points (95% CI [2.76, 3.85], $p < 10^{-67}$, $r = 0.40$). Comparable improvements were found in the Lower scenario, where median FIA rose by 8.02 points (95 % CI [6.87, 9.18], $p < 10^{-82}$, $r = 0.45$) and the percentage of affordable structures increased by 3.24 points (95 % CI [2.72, 3.76], $p < 10^{-63}$, $r = 0.39$). Across all years, effect sizes ranged from 0.21 to 0.49, indicating small-to-moderate but consistent practical significance. These results confirm that the improvements in affordability associated

with MP23 projects are not only numerically meaningful but also statistically significant at the block-group level.

Table 2. Paired block-group comparisons of FWOA and FWMP outcomes across scenarios and years. Reported metrics include mean differences (Δ), 95% confidence intervals, p-values, and effect sizes (r), for both median FIA and percent affordable structures.

Metric	Scenario	Year	Mean Δ	95% CI Low	95% CI High	p-value	Effect (r)
Median FIA	Higher	12	1.2422	1.0028	1.4815	4.67E-61	0.384318
	Higher	22	1.9438	1.3075	2.5801	1.49E-37	0.298575
	Higher	32	5.244	4.4191	6.0689	1.86E-71	0.416703
	Higher	42	7.7449	6.613	8.8769	3.20E-91	0.472202
	Higher	52	8.158	6.9566	9.3595	5.66E-97	0.487172
	Lower	12	1.0476	0.8514	1.2439	7.05E-59	0.377184
	Lower	22	2.038	1.3881	2.688	1.72E-44	0.326217
	Lower	32	2.7033	1.9755	3.4311	3.29E-41	0.313439
	Lower	42	5.4066	4.5724	6.2408	3.62E-77	0.433467
	Lower	52	8.0208	6.865	9.1767	4.58E-82	0.447344
% Affordable Structures	Higher	12	0.6051	0.4621	0.7481	5.27E-42	0.316582
	Higher	22	0.6552	0.3136	0.9968	1.87E-19	0.210297
	Higher	32	2.2143	1.8019	2.6266	9.10E-49	0.342151
	Higher	42	3.112	2.5918	3.6321	6.37E-63	0.390324
	Higher	52	3.3042	2.7559	3.8525	1.84E-67	0.404569
	Lower	12	0.5175	0.3966	0.6385	1.09E-40	0.31137
	Lower	22	0.7131	0.3922	1.0341	2.20E-26	0.247778
	Lower	32	1.0354	0.665	1.4058	8.41E-25	0.239722
	Lower	42	2.3126	1.9002	2.725	4.56E-56	0.367776
	Lower	52	3.2384	2.7173	3.7595	3.86E-63	0.391018

These findings demonstrate that the implementation of MP23 projects would contribute not only to physical risk reduction but also to economic resilience, making insurance more attainable for a larger portion of the population over time.

3.2.2 Interpretation

Although the percentage improvements appear modest, the implications are significant when scaled across thousands of households. For example, a 3% increase in affordability would translate to tens of thousands of additional homes having access to affordable flood insurance coverage, particularly in vulnerable communities. These gains correspond to substantial reductions in premium expenditures at the household and regional scale, as detailed in Section 3.2.4, which examines the aggregate dollar savings associated with MP23 project implementation.

However, it is important to note that RR2.0 does not currently incorporate most implemented Louisiana Coastal Master Plan project impacts into premium calculations. To be included, they must be formally recognized through FEMA mapping or rating system updates. Therefore, these modeled results represent the potential premium savings and affordability

improvements that would occur if FEMA fully integrated master plan project outcomes into its pricing engine.

To spatially visualize the potential benefits of MP23 restoration and risk reduction projects on insurance affordability, Figure 3 maps the change in the percentage of affordable structures between Year 12 and Year 52 under FWMP Higher scenario and Figure 4 presents the net change in the percentage of affordable structures between the FWMP and FWOA scenarios from Year 12 to Year 52. This map highlights the predicted difference in affordability outcomes attributable to MP23 interventions, where positive values indicate block groups that experienced reduced affordability loss or even improvement under FWMP compared to FWOA. The spatial pattern reveals that many areas are predicted to benefit substantially from MP23 projects, while a few regions saw minimal or no improvement, suggesting a potential need for targeted future investments.

Figure 3. Change in percent Affordability – Year 12 to 52 (FWMP, Higher)

Figure 4. Net Improvement in Flood Insurance Affordability Due to MP23 Restoration and Risk Reduction Project Implementation (Δ % Affordable, FWMP – FWOA, Year 12 to 52, Higher)

3.2.3 Block Groups with Greatest Affordability Decline

To assess the effectiveness of MP23 projects on the affordability, we focused on the 10 census block groups that experienced the largest drop in affordability. Table 3 presents the percentage point change in affordability (% of structures with $FIA \geq 100$) for these Census block group IDs (GEOIDs). Table 3 reports each block group's change under FWOA and FWMP and classifies the FWMP outcome relative to its FWOA trajectory as Hold the line, Mitigated, No effect, or Worse.

Table 3. Change in % Affordable Structures ($FIA \geq 100$) Between Year 12 and Year 52 (Top 10 Worst-Affected Block Groups Under FWOA, Higher). Changes are percentage points (pp).

block group ID	Δ % Affordable (FWOA)	Δ % Affordable (FWMP)	Category
221090002033	-96.61	-88.71	Mitigated
221090004023	-94.75	-96.18	Worse
220450304025	-89.72	-1.19	Mitigated
220450312004	-86.59	-0.61	Mitigated
220450301017	-85.71	-31.93	Mitigated
221090004022	-83.71	-92.83	Worse
220450312001	-83.7	0	Hold the line

220450310001	-81.98	-5.52	Mitigated
220450309001	-81.86	-0.49	Hold the line
220450309006	-81.82	-0.83	Mitigated

Among the 10 most impacted block groups under FWOA, FWMP implementation prevented any decline in affordability in six cases (Mitigated), reduced the severity of decline in two cases (hold the line), and failed to improve affordability in the remaining two (Worse). Under FWOA, these block groups experienced severe declines in affordability, ranging from –82% to –97%. While some block groups saw notable reductions in the severity of decline under FWMP (e.g., block group ID 220450312001 in Iberia Parish improved from –83.7%+ to 0%), several others continued to deteriorate or even worsened (e.g., block group ID 221090004023 declined further from –94.75% under FWOA to –96.18% under FWMP). This contrast highlights that these areas may require further intervention.

This localized comparison clarifies where MP23 projects effectively “hold the line,” where they meaningfully mitigate losses, and where additional policy, financial, or engineering measures may be warranted. The spatial context for these patterns is provided by Figure 3 and Figure 4, and the complete block-group results for all years, both scenarios, and both plans are available in Supplementary Data S1 (Excel).

To supplement the main results, we also generated maps of the percent of structures classified as affordable (i.e., those with FIA \geq 100) for select future year, scenario, and planning condition. These maps visually represent the distribution of affordability across census block groups and provide additional context on how affordability varies both spatially and temporally across the coastal region. The maps are included in Appendix A and are organized by year and scenario to facilitate comparison.

3.2.4 Insurance Premium Reduction

In addition to estimating FIA metrics, we quantified the direct premium impact of MP23 restoration and risk reduction projects implementation by comparing modeled RR2.0 premiums. Figure 5 summarizes modeled results for total RR2.0 premiums under both FWOA and FWMP conditions across the Higher and Lower environmental scenarios. The modeled results indicate that premiums are projected to increase steadily over time under the FWOA condition. However, under the FWMP condition, premiums grow much more slowly, showing that MP23 restoration and risk reduction project implementation helps flatten the upward trend in coastwide flood insurance costs.

Under the Higher scenario, total premiums increase from approximately \$1.70 billion in Year 12 to \$1.91 billion by Year 52 under the FWOA condition, an increase of about \$205 million (+12%) over the 50-year planning horizon. With FWMP, premiums rise more slowly, reaching about \$1.75 billion by Year 52. This corresponds to an annual net savings of \$156 million at Year 52 compared to the FWOA condition. The difference between FWOA and FWMP widens steadily over time, with \$39 million in savings at Year 12, \$59 million by Year 22, \$110 million by Year 32, and \$150 million by Year 42, before stabilizing around \$156 million by Year 52.

Figure 5. (a) Total Premiums Over 50 Years, Future With and Without Action, Higher and Lower Scenario; (b) annual premium savings (FWMP–FWOA) Over 50 Years, Higher and Lower Scenario.

The Lower scenario follows a similar trend but with slightly smaller magnitudes. Total premiums increase from \$1.70 billion in Year 12 to \$1.82 billion in Year 52 under FWOA, while the FWMP condition results in \$1.68 billion at Year 52. The annual difference between the two conditions grows from \$37 million in Year 12 to \$143 million in Year 52, indicating that the FWMP provides consistent and compounding economic benefits even under a less severe environmental future.

We also examined the spatial distribution of premium savings at the census block-group level. Figure 6 illustrates the difference between FWMP and FWOA premiums for the Higher scenario at Year 12 and Year 22, showing where MP23 restoration and risk reduction projects yield the most substantial economic impacts.

Figure 6. Insurance Premium Savings (USD) at Block-group Level, (a) Year 12, Higher; (b) Year 22, Higher.

Taken together, these results demonstrate that the MP23 projects reduce coastwide insurance costs by approximately 8–9% by Year 52, yielding annual benefits exceeding \$150 million. Although this reduction may not immediately translate into improved short-term affordability for all households, it represents a significant long-term financial benefit that

prevents further erosion of affordability and sustains access to insurance coverage across coastal communities.

4.0 Conclusions

This analysis provides a comprehensive assessment of flood insurance affordability across coastal Louisiana under FEMA's Risk Rating 2.0 (RR2.0) framework. Using a structure-level affordability metric (FIA) based on ACS median income and full-risk premiums, we quantified both the baseline affordability landscape and the long-term implications of future risk scenarios. Key findings include:

- Under the MP23 FWOA condition, flood insurance affordability is projected to deteriorate significantly across the region, particularly in low-lying, economically vulnerable block groups.
 - Several communities already face unaffordable flood insurance premiums as early as model Year 12, and many of these same areas experience the sharpest declines over time.
- Modeling results under the FWMP condition show that implementing MP23 restoration and risk reduction projects can reduce affordability losses, especially in areas where large-scale levees and marsh creation projects are implemented.
 - Although the average percentage-point improvements appear modest (~3% increase in affordable structures by Year 52), the number of households affected is substantial, translating to millions of dollars in avoided premium costs. These reductions represent cumulative savings exceeding \$140 million by Year 52 under the both Higher and Lower scenario, highlighting the meaningful economic impact of MP23 project implementation.
 - Despite improvements in some areas, many block groups still show steep affordability declines, and some are in worse shape with MP23 implementation than without. This highlights the need for targeted policy support, federal recognition of project impacts, and integrated strategies that combine structural, financial, and regulatory solutions.

This work underscores the importance of embedding affordability considerations into coastal planning. Louisiana's Coastal Master Plan has the potential to significantly improve flood resilience and reduce economic vulnerability. Our paired block-group analysis demonstrates that FWMP implementation yields statistically significant gains in affordability ($p < 0.001$ across all scenarios), increasing the proportion of affordable structures by 3 percentage points and raising median FIA by 6–8 points by Year 52. These findings underscore that resilience benefits are significant, provided they are captured in insurance pricing and made accessible to the communities that need them most.

References

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Appendix A. Spatial Distribution of Flood Insurance Affordability (FIA ≥ 100)

This appendix includes block group-level maps showing the percent of structures meeting the affordability threshold (FIA ≥ 100) across different planning horizons and scenarios.

A.1 Higher Scenario – FWOA

Figure A1.1: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA ≥ 100) – Year 12 – Higher Scenario – FWOA

Figure A1.2: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA ≥ 100) – Year 22 – Higher Scenario – FWOA

Figure A1.3: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA \geq 100) – Year 32 – Higher Scenario – FWOA

Figure A1.4: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA \geq 100) – Year 42 – Higher Scenario – FWOA

Figure A1.5: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA \geq 100) – Year 52 – Higher Scenario – FWOA

A.2 Lower Scenario – FWOA

Figure A2.1: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 12 – Lower Scenario – FWOA

Figure A2.2: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 22 – Lower Scenario – FWOA

Figure A2.3: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 32 – Lower Scenario – FWOA

Figure A2.4: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 42 – Lower Scenario – FWOA

Figure A2.5: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 52 – Lower Scenario – FWOA

A.3 Higher Scenario – FWMP

Figure A3.1: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA \geq 100) – Year 12 – Higher Scenario – FWMP

Figure A3.2: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA \geq 100) – Year 22 – Higher Scenario – FWMP

Figure A3.3: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA \geq 100) – Year 32 – Higher Scenario – FWMP

Figure A3.4: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA ≥ 100) – Year 42 – Higher Scenario – FWMP

Figure A3.5: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria (FIA ≥ 100) – Year 52 – Higher Scenario – FWMP

A.4 Lower Scenario – FWMP

Figure A4.1: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 12 – Lower Scenario – FWMP

Figure A4.2: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 22 – Lower Scenario – FWMP

Figure A4.3: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 32 – Lower Scenario – FWMP

Figure A4.4: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 42 – Lower Scenario – FWMP

Figure A4.5: Percent of structures meeting affordability criteria ($FIA \geq 100$) – Year 52 – Lower Scenario – FWMP

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Data S1 (Excel) provides block-group metrics for Years 12, 22, 32, 42, and 52 under FWOA and FWMP for both Higher/Lower scenarios. For each (Scenario, Year, Plan, block group ID), the file includes median FIA, % affordable ($FIA \geq 100$), structure counts, FWMP–FWOA deltas by year, Year 12→52 changes within each plan, a “net improvement” (FWMP – FWOA) metric, and a categorical outcome label (Hold the line / Mitigated / No effect / Worse). A README/Data Dictionary sheet describes column definitions, formulas, and thresholds.